

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SYSTEMS IN THE EDUCATIONAL
PROCESS

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Abstract

The article discusses modern approaches and the role of artificial intelligence technologies in the educational process. The relevance of the topic and its theoretical foundations are also presented. The main purpose of the article is to identify and evaluate the means of using artificial intelligence achievements in teaching information technology. The importance of the means of using artificial intelligence achievements in the educational process and recommendations for future research are given.

Annotatsiya

Maqolada zamonaviy yondashuvlar va sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni haqida fikr yuritiladi. Shuningdek, mavzuning dolzarbligi va uning nazariy asoslari taqdim etiladi. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi axborot texnologiyalari fanini o'qitishda sun'iy intellekt yutuqlaridan foydalanish vositalarini aniqlash va baholashdir. Sun'iy intellekt yutuqlaridan ta'lim jarayonida foydalanish vositalarining ahamiyati va kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar uchun yo'naltirilgan tavsiyalar beriladi.

Keywords: *medicine, engineering and industry, education, artificial intelligence, methodological methods, educational technologies, educational process, innovative approaches.*

Kalit so'zlar: *tibbiyot, muhandislik va sanoat sohalari, o'qitish, sun'iy intellekt, metodik usullar, ta'lim texnologiyalari, o'quv jarayoni, innovatsion yondashuvlar.*

Artificial intelligence has become one of the most important technologies in the world today. Many of the scenes that we could only see in movies and various science fiction novels at the beginning of the last century are becoming a reality with the advent of artificial intelligence in our lives. In the current environment, when it is estimated that about a quarter of the world's gross domestic product will depend on digital technologies, paying special attention to the acceleration and development of work in this area is the most correct strategic direction. Today, in world practice, countries such as Canada, Singapore, the United Arab Emirates, Finland, Japan, China, Italy, Tunisia, the United Kingdom, the United States, Sweden, Mexico, the European Union, Kenya, Denmark, France, Australia, the Republic of Korea, India and Germany have announced strategies for the development of artificial intelligence. The rapid and widespread use of artificial intelligence technologies in world practice and the availability of such digital information to ensure high-quality use in our country's life, as well as the creation of favorable conditions for the training of qualified personnel in this field, are the requirements of today. The term artificial intelligence was first proposed by John McCarthy and his colleagues Marvin Lee Minsky, Nathaniel Rochester, and Claude Shannon at the Dortmund conference in 1956. John McCarthy is considered the author of this term. During this time, a huge amount of scientific research has been and is being conducted, as a result of which the scope of application of artificial intelligence is rapidly expanding.

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Before defining the concept of artificial intelligence, we need to know what intelligence is.

Intelligence - (lat. intellectus - knowledge, understanding, perception, mind) is a person's mental ability; the ability to accurately reflect and change life and the environment in the mind, to think, read, learn, know the world and perceive social experience; the ability to make decisions when solving various problems, act rationally, and foresee events. Intelligence includes perception, memory, thinking, and mental processes. The development of intelligence depends on social factors such as innate talent, brain capabilities, active activity, and life experience. The level of intelligence is determined by human activity and the results of psychological tests.

From the concept of "intelligence" considered above, it can be concluded that intelligence belongs only to humans and is a specific measure of human mental abilities. Psychologists have developed the ability to determine the intellectual (mental) level of a person through experiments using special methods. The definitions of the concepts of artificial intelligence and intelligence differ from each other. The main reason for this is that the properties of the brain have not yet been fully studied. The human brain contains countless secrets. However, we do not fully know the methods and principles of how the human brain works, our basic knowledge of how the brain works is limited to neurons and their activities. In order to study the brain to the maximum, it is first necessary to understand and explain how the brain works. As a result, neuroscience and, accordingly, a brain-based educational approach were formed. By analyzing the algorithm of the brain's operation, a significant contribution can be made to the development of computers or intelligent machines.

The experiences of developed countries in using artificial intelligence systems in education, as well as the issues of their application in our country's education, were studied.

The author of the term artificial intelligence, John McCarthy, himself, gave several definitions of artificial intelligence. He defined artificial intelligence as "the science and engineering of creating intelligent machines similar to humans, especially intelligent computer programs." Accordingly, a computer can be described as artificial intelligence if it demonstrates human-like behaviors such as thinking, solving problems, creating meaning, and generalizing, that is, if it can use high-level cognitive abilities.

According to another great scientist, Nils Nilsson, who is known for his research on artificial intelligence and the author of numerous scientific publications in this field, "artificial intelligence is a theory aimed at creating an imitation of natural intelligence." This can also be defined as follows, that is, artificial intelligence - a sequence of algorithms that imitate human intelligence.

From the above, we can understand that research on artificial intelligence emphasizes that everything in the universe works within a certain algorithm. Accordingly, consciousness is the result of a mathematically very complex algorithm. For most authors of artificial intelligence today, the brain is a structure that performs its functions based on the laws of the external world. This means that artificial intelligence has a rational nature.

The development and transformation of artificial intelligence parallels the development of computers, namely transistors. However, this idea should not lead to the conclusion that artificial intelligence is only related to computer technology. On the contrary, it indicates that artificial intelligence is a field that is directly related to many disciplines, from medicine, engineering and industry to psychology, and is structured in accordance with the needs of all of them. Currently, artificial intelligence can be divided into three types based on its capabilities, according to the analysis of various scientific literature.

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Weak artificial intelligence is a type of artificial intelligence that is capable of performing a specific task with intelligence, and is the most common and currently available type.

Narrow AI cannot operate outside its domain and limitations, as it is designed for only one specific task. That is why it is also called narrow AI. Apple's Siri program is a good example of narrow AI, which operates within a limited range of types and predefined capabilities. Other examples of narrow AI include playing chess, the operation of self-driving cars, speech recognition, and image recognition.

General artificial intelligence is a type of intelligence that can perform any intellectual task as efficiently as a human. General artificial intelligence is a system that is intelligent and thinks like a human. Currently, there is no such system that represents general artificial intelligence and can perform any task as perfectly as a human. Researchers around the world are now focusing on developing machines with general artificial intelligence. Research on systems with general artificial intelligence is still ongoing, and creating such systems requires a lot of effort and time.

Artificial intelligence is a branch of computer science that deals with the creation of computer systems with capabilities typically associated with human intelligence: language understanding, learning, reasoning, problem solving, translation, etc. Currently, artificial intelligence consists of algorithms and software systems designed to perform various tasks and can perform many of the tasks that human intelligence can perform.

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